

FORMATION OF INFORMATION CULTURE OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES

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Abstract: This article describes the importance and methods of forming the information culture of children with disabilities, as well as issues of helping them find their place in society. The article examines ways to achieve successful integration of children into society through the use of modern information technologies, their application in the educational process, increasing media literacy and a psychological-pedagogical approach. Technologies that help them adapt to social and cultural life through art therapy, bibliotherapy and other creative activities are also analyzed.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada imkoniyati cheklangan bolalarning axborot madaniyatini shakllantirishning ahamiyati va usullari, shuningdek, ularning jamiyatdagi o‘rnini topishga ko‘maklashish masalalari yoritilgan. Maqolada zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish, ularni ta’lim jarayonida qo‘llash, media savodxonlikni oshirish va psixologik-pedagogik yondashuv orqali bolalarning jamiyatga muvaffaqiyatli integratsiyasiga erishish usullari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, san’at terapiyasi, biblioterapiya va boshqa ijodiy faoliyatlar orqali ularni ijtimoiy va madaniy hayotga moslashuviga yordam beruvchi texnologiyalar tahlil qilinadi.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны значение и методы формирования информационной культуры детей с ограниченными возможностями, а также вопросы помощи им в поиске своего места в обществе. В статье рассматриваются пути достижения успешной интеграции детей в общество посредством использования современных информационных технологий, их применения в образовательном процессе, повышения медиаграмотности и психолого-педагогического подхода. Также анализируются технологии, которые помогают им адаптироваться к социальной и культурной жизни посредством арт-терапии, библиотерапии и другой творческой деятельности.

Key words: Children with disabilities, information technologies, rehabilitation, methodological methods.

The modern socio-cultural situation and the development of market relations, in general, have had a negative impact on the vulnerable sections of the population, including the disabled, who are deprived of the opportunity to have a full economic, political and cultural life. In the conditions of such intense social changes, the previous mechanisms of social support and protection of the population are ineffective, and new ones have not been formed. In recent years, despite measures taken at the state level to combat social risks, large amounts of money have been directed to support children with disabilities (the state program “Available environment” is being implemented, inclusive ta The activity of the state policy and other subjects is not effective enough for people with disabilities. As a burden” is determined by the paradigm of existing ideas about the environment of disability⁷⁸. It should be taken into account that the full integration of disabled people into society cannot be achieved, because serious health defects (deafness, blindness, mental retardation, movement system diseases) cannot be fully compensated. Therefore, the “uniqueness” of the position of disabled people in society remains. Allows equal use of independent life, self-determination and freedom of choice. Creating conditions to minimize the consequences of negative events, taking measures to realize the social rights and opportunities of disabled people is of urgent importance at the level of the state and society. Wider use of pedagogical opportunities and technologies by institutions of a social, cultural and educational nature at the regional level, ensuring adaptation and integration of disabled people, socio-cultural rehabilitation.

Every person born today must find his place in the future. In such cases, there are few difficulties for persons with disabilities. Introduction of information technologies to such people in teaching processes, distance education. Facilities were created for them to acquire theoretical and practical skills. The field of digitalization of modern education is wide-ranging and includes the use of information technologies in the educational process and outside the classroom, testing students, recording achievements, etc. Its main goal is to increase the effectiveness of the education and training process. In vocational schools, information technologies can be used not only to improve methodological approaches to education aimed at developing intellectual potential, but also to form professional competencies of students. Innovation (English innovation) is innovation. A.I. Prigogine understands innovation as purposeful changes that introduce a new, relatively stable element to a specific social unit, organization, population, society, group. This is an innovator’s activity. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the pedagogical process and teacher’s and student’s activities, and mainly interactive methods are fully used in its implementation. Interactive methods are called collective thinking, that is, methods of pedagogical influence, which are part of the educational content.

⁷⁸ <https://cyberleninka.r>

The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and students.

Information technology has a special place in the rehabilitation of students with disabilities and disabilities. Vocational school, as a rule, students with various disabilities, as well as students with disabilities, study, and for each student, depending on his illness, certain methodological methods and methods are used in the lesson. Naturally, these methods are different for students with hearing, vision, intelligence, as well as for people with disorders of the locomotor system. Purposeful use of computers in the process of education and upbringing of disabled students and disabled children, taking into account individual educational opportunities and needs of students, allows to create optimal psychological and pedagogical conditions for correction and compensation of violations in children. As much as possible. The main directions of using information technologies in computer classes are as follows:

1. Helping students acquire strong computer skills, as many students are homeschooled and lack knowledge;
2. Study and analysis of educational material presented in electronic media. For students with visual impairments, all lecture materials are provided in electronic form with the ability to increase the font size;
3. The use of the “Mytest” test shell allows you to create verification tests that take into account the intellectual abilities of students, while at the same time it is convenient to check the knowledge and skills of students with impaired speech development;

Presentation of a computer presentation, including an interactive presentation. One of the main advantages of using information technologies in the education of children with disabilities is to visualize the educational material presented to them.

Is the magnitude of the ability and visual display of information is any human activity

1. Helps increase efficiency:
2. Use of electronic textbooks, Internet and ICT;
3. Virtual laboratories, museums;
4. Distance learning, e-mail.

For the teacher, the use of the interactive whiteboard at all stages of the lesson, especially at the stage of reflection, has become important for students with disabilities. MS Word text for students with disabilities. Editor, MS Excel spreadsheets, etc. Specially designed electronic laboratory and practical work to facilitate data entry is used. It should be noted that college students actively participate in online olympiads in informatics and ICT, information technologies in professional activities, as well as other studied subjects. They also participate in various scientific and practical conferences using information technologies. Many students became winners, which serves to develop educational and psychological motivation of students, creative abilities. Thus, the implementation of modern

information technology opportunities in computer science classes expands the types of educational activities, improves the existing ones, and creates new organizational forms and teaching methods. The lesson for handicapped and disabled children using modern information technologies helps to develop individuality, professional rehabilitation⁷⁹.

Rehabilitation of disabled children and the specified direction of integration is carried out by filling the content with certain types of socio-cultural activities. The following have rehabilitation potential: artistic and creative (practical art, theater, dance, musical activities), game, technical, sports, tourism and other types of socio-cultural activities. These types form the basis of rehabilitation technologies: art therapy, bibliotherapy, music therapy, play therapy, etc. The psychological-pedagogical direction of rehabilitation of disabled children occupies a leading position in the field of psychological rehabilitation and psychological-pedagogical correction, because the problem of disabled children is not limited to the medical-pedagogical aspect, it has a special status in the social context. Minimize unequal opportunities. The basis of this direction is psychological rehabilitation and psychological-pedagogical correction, which helps to eliminate the imbalance in mental development in the general complex of rehabilitation measures and provides the opportunity to fully integrate disabled children into social and cultural life. Society. These two directions (social-cultural and psychological-pedagogical) are aimed at developing cultural skills and psychological attitudes that allow disabled children to be successful in society, to achieve a high level of self-awareness in work and leisure activities. The main tasks of the psychological-pedagogical direction, which ensures the rehabilitation of the disabled, are as follows: restoration and development of individual intellectual functions (psychomotor skills, memory, perception, speech, thinking, etc.).

Teaching media literacy to children with disabilities means developing their skills to receive, analyze and effectively use information. There are a number of methods and approaches to effectively implement this process.

1. Games and Interactive Activities

–Role-playing games: Children learn the reasons for media literacy, such as evaluating information correctly or conveying it without errors. Through games, they communicate with each other and exchange ideas.

VIRTUAL GUARDIANS: Through hands-on activities and simulations, children can test different media sources and learn what to trust and when to be suspicious.

2. Analyzing Media Sources

⁷⁹ Nabiyeva, G. A. (2021). *IMKONIYATI CHEKLANGAN BOLALARNING TA'LIM-TARBIYA OLISHLARI*. Scientific progress.

–Review with me: Introducing and evaluating different media sources (newspaper, television, internet). Children can identify what information these sources contain and discuss the reliability of each source.

–Expanded Interests: Invite children to choose media resources on a variety of topics, then help them analyze their content. They must express their opinions and provide reasons for their analysis.

3. Cooperation with parents and teachers

–Information sessions: Organize media literacy workshops for parents and teachers to inform them about the importance of media literacy and how to help children.

–Reading together: Parents and children read and discuss books, articles or internet resources together. This allows children to learn how to correctly interpret information.

4. Use of Technological Tools

–Special programs: Application of media literacy programs and applications developed for children with disabilities. These programs should be interactive and fun, help children develop media literacy skills.

–Video and Audio Resources: Children can learn media literacy by watching or listening to a variety of video and audio materials. By discussing these, it helps children learn new skills.

5. Other Primary Education

–Preparation for scenes: Teaching children skills on how to prepare and convey information. They can make videos on a topic of their choice.

–Critical Thinking: Helping children develop critical thinking skills and evaluating information sources. They should learn to ask questions about the information sources they use⁸⁰.

Summary: It is important to use different methods to develop media literacy in children with disabilities, to expand their abilities and prepare them for active participation in society. These methods allow children to develop the skills of using media resources correctly, evaluating information and expressing their opinions. In the process of adapting to the individual needs of each child and supporting him, the activity of parents, teachers and society is necessary.

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